

POLICY BRIEF

Exploratory Cost-Effectiveness Analysis of Digital Rehabilitation Services

Use of the Inclusion App for Persons with Low Back Pain in Rwanda

Digital rehabilitation offers a promising approach to scaling up healthcare delivery and improving patient access, particularly in resource-limited settings. However, despite this potential, evidence on real-world cost-effectiveness remains limited. This policy brief presents early findings from a study **comparing costs and health-related quality of life outcomes among persons with low back pain receiving either 1) standard physiotherapy services or 2) digital rehabilitation delivered through the Inclusion App in Rwanda**. These findings provide emerging evidence to inform healthcare policy discussions on the role of digital rehabilitation services.

THE PROJECT

The Jamk University of Applied Sciences partners in Rwanda, with the University of Rwanda and its Centre of Excellence in Biomedical Engineering and eHealth (CEBE) that serves as the primary implementing partner and local lead.

Within this framework, Physitrack and Physiotools developed the Inclusion App to improve access to rehabilitation services in underserved settings, including Rwanda, Indonesia, Kenya, and Tanzania. By leveraging digital technologies, the app enables physiotherapists and community health workers (CHWs) to deliver scalable and cost-effective rehabilitation services. To date, the programme has reached more than 15,000 users across these countries.

The **Inclusion App** is a mobile health solution designed by clinical professionals for independent use by individual users. It delivers structured exercise programmes that support CHWs in providing early-phase rehabilitation for common musculoskeletal conditions, including low back pain, neck pain, and arthritis.

WHY LOW BACK PAIN?

Low back pain was selected for analysis because it was the **most prevalent condition among Inclusion App users**. Specifically, 51.6% of the 6,809 clients used low back pain exercise programmes. Other commonly used programmes addressed shoulder conditions (17.4%) and hip arthritis (6.2%). This pattern is consistent with the high global prevalence of low back pain, which affects approximately 70 per 1,000 people and represents the most common musculoskeletal disorder worldwide [1]. In addition, low back pain was selected because **comparable rehabilitation services are available within Rwanda's public healthcare system** for a similar patient population. This enables meaningful comparisons of costs and outcomes between digital rehabilitation and standard physiotherapy services.

PARTICIPANTS

A total of **94 individuals with low back pain** from Rwanda's Northern Province were included in the study. Of these, **45 received physiotherapy services through the public health system** at Ruhengeri Referral and Teaching

RECOMMENDATIONS

- ▶ **Scale up digital rehabilitation solutions for people with low back pain.**
- ▶ **Assess the suitability of digital rehabilitation for other musculoskeletal disorders.**
- ▶ **Explore reimbursement options, tokens or performance-based financing, for digital rehabilitation.**
- ▶ **Develop and implement training programmes for community health workers.**
- ▶ **Integrate digital rehabilitation tools with existing physiotherapy services.**

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PHYSIOTHERAPY PATHWAY

DIGITAL REHABILITATION PATHWAY

Figure 1: Flowchart illustrating the steps and timelines of the two care pathways: 1) Physiotherapy, and 2) Digital Rehabilitation.

Hospital and Butaro Level 2 Hospital, while the remaining **49 received digital rehabilitation** via the Inclusion App, accessed through community health workers (CHWs).

Participant selection was based on the following criteria: completion of low back pain treatment within the preceding two months, residence in Musanze or Burera districts, and willingness to participate in the survey. To protect participant confidentiality, no demographic or clinical history data were collected.

CARE PATHWAYS

Two care pathways for individuals with low back pain were compared (Figure 1).

1. The standard physiotherapy pathway involves three nursing consultations at primary health centres, followed by referral to a district hospital physician. A subset of these patients is subsequently referred to hospital-based physiotherapy services. Patients are assumed to receive an average of five physiotherapy sessions, each lasting 30 minutes. Access to physiotherapy through this pathway is often delayed and limited for many patients.

2. The digital rehabilitation pathway begins with a consultation where a CHW introduces and trains participants to use the Inclusion App. CHWs also identify warning signs throughout the rehabilitation process that require

immediate referral. Participants then use the application to do the recommended exercises independently. This approach allows more users to start guided low-back exercises sooner. On average, persons in the sample completed the digital rehabilitation pathway in 6 months.

COSTS

The costs of the two care pathways were analysed and compared from the **healthcare payer perspective**. Direct costs included reimbursement fees for consultations and X-rays, gross salary costs for medical personnel consultation time, community health worker (CHW)

allowances, CHW training costs, and Inclusion App user fees. Costs related to pain medication, patient out-of-pocket payments, and travel expenses were excluded. All costs are reported in 2025 Rwandan Francs (RWF) and converted to US dollars using an exchange rate of 1 USD = 1,446 RWF (31 December 2025)

For the standard **physiotherapy** pathway, costs comprised reimbursement fees for physician consultations and a lumbosacral X-ray covered by the Community-Based Health Insurance, as well as gross salary costs for consultation time paid by the Ministry of Health [2,3]. Service use included three 10-minute nursing

Figure 2: Direct healthcare payer costs per person with low-back pain for the physiotherapy pathway and the digital rehabilitation pathway using the Inclusion App.

Figure 3: Health states reported with the visual analogue scale (VAS) at baseline, one month, and three months for persons with low back pain following the physiotherapy pathway and the digital rehabilitation pathway.

Figure 4: Development of health states over the three-month period and total Quality-Adjusted Life Years (QALYs) gained per person for the physiotherapy pathway and the digital rehabilitation pathway using the Inclusion App.

consultations, one physician consultation, and five 30-minute physiotherapy sessions delivered by physiotherapists. The total cost of the standard pathway was **RWF 184,308 (US\$126.54) per patient** (Figure 2).

In the **digital rehabilitation** pathway, CHWs are unsalaried volunteers. During the pilot phase, they received a monthly transport allowance of RWF 10,000 (not intended for national-scale implementation) and a monthly internet allowance of RWF 3,000. CHWs completed a half-day initial training on the Inclusion App, followed by a refresher session after one month. Allowance and training costs were allocated across all 6,809 Inclusion App users during the pilot. The cost of access to the low back pain exercise programme was RWF 1,456 (US\$1.00) per user, resulting in a total digital pathway cost of **RWF 2,770 (US\$1.95) per user**. Compared to the standard physiotherapy pathway, using the **Inclusion App costs 67 times less per person** with low back pain.

EFFECTIVENESS

Effectiveness was assessed using the **EQ-5D-5L quality of life questionnaire**, a widely used instrument measuring health status across five dimensions: mobility, self-care, usual activities, pain/discomfort, and anxiety/depression. Data were collected through telephone interviews at three time points: baseline

(when participants first sought care for low back pain from a nurse or community health worker), one month, and three months.

The EQ-5D-5L also includes a **visual analogue scale (VAS)**, which captures respondents' **self-rated overall health status** on the day of the interview. The scale ranges from 0, representing the worst imaginable health, to 100, representing the best imaginable health. Figure 3 presents VAS scores for both care pathways. At baseline, individuals using the Inclusion App reported slightly poorer health status than those receiving standard physiotherapy. By one month, however, the Inclusion App group demonstrated greater improvement, a difference that persisted at the three-month follow-up.

QUALITY OF LIFE

Health state measurements were converted into **quality-adjusted life years (QALYs)** to capture both the severity and duration of health improvements. Over the three-month period, the **digital rehabilitation** pathway resulted in higher quality of life gains, with **0.17 QALYs per user**, compared with **0.13 QALYs per patient** in the standard **physiotherapy** pathway (Figure 4). On the vertical scale, 1.00 represents full health and 0.00 represents death.

This corresponds to a **32% higher QALY gain per person** with low back pain in the digital rehabilitation pathway than in the standard physiotherapy pathway. These results indicate that the Inclusion App achieved greater health gains over the study period while using fewer healthcare resources. Overall, the findings support the potential value of digital rehabilitation as part of routine care.

COST-EFFECTIVENESS

The incremental cost-effectiveness ratio (ICER) compares differences in costs and health outcomes between the standard physiotherapy and digital rehabilitation pathways. Over the three-month period, the **digital rehabilitation** pathway had lower costs, with an incremental **cost saving of RWF 181,537 per person**, and **higher health gains**, with an additional **0.04 QALYs per person**. Dividing incremental costs by incremental QALYs results in an ICER of **-RWF 4.4 million per QALY (-USD 3,043 per QALY)**.

The negative ICER indicates that the **digital rehabilitation pathway dominates standard physiotherapy**, as it produces **better health outcomes at lower cost**. These findings provide strong evidence that **the Inclusion App represents a cost-effective alternative for the treatment of low back pain** and supports its consideration as a **preferred option for the Ministry of Health**.

CONCLUSION

The digital rehabilitation pathway using the Inclusion App demonstrated improved health outcomes for patients with low back pain in Rwanda compared with standard physiotherapy services. These effects are likely driven by faster and broader access to care enabled through community health workers (CHWs) and digital delivery. Importantly, the digital pathway is substantially less expensive and reduces pressure on healthcare personnel. Together, these findings show that digital rehabilitation can improve patient outcomes while using considerably fewer healthcare resources.

LIMITATIONS

These results provide an early indication of the cost-effectiveness of digital rehabilitation services. However, some limitations should be noted. The sample size is relatively small, and the follow-up period is short. Consequently, the findings should be interpreted as approximate and exploratory rather than definitive.

RECOMMENDATIONS

- 1. Scale up digital rehabilitation solutions**, such as the Inclusion App, through community health workers to improve access to care for people with low back pain.
- 2. Evaluate the suitability and effectiveness of digital rehabilitation for other musculoskeletal conditions**, prioritising those with high prevalence and disease severity.
- 3. Explore reimbursement mechanisms for digital rehabilitation** within the community-based health insurance system, including innovative payment models such as token-based approaches or performance-based financing.
- 4. Develop and implement training programmes for community health workers** to support the rapid and sustained adoption of digital rehabilitation solutions.
- 5. Integrate digital rehabilitation tools into existing physiotherapy services**, complementary rather than substitute interventions.

ETHICAL CLEARANCE

Ethical clearance for this study was granted by the Rwanda National Research Ethics Committee under the Ministry of Health (RNEC515/2024, issued on 22 August 2024).

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This study forms part of the NextStep to Scale: Advancing Digital Rehabilitation in East Africa and Southeast Asia project, coordinated by JAMK University of Applied Sciences in collaboration with Phys-iostools Ltd. and GoodLife Technology Ltd. The project is financed by the Ministry for Foreign Affairs of Finland / Finnpartnership.

The authors thank the University of Rwanda, its Centre of Excellence in Biomedical Engineering and eHealth (CEBE), the community health workers, patients, hospital administration, Physitrack personnel, Dr Christine Mpundu-Kaambwa, Dr Eeva Aartolahti, Dr Michael Oduor, Dr Katariina Korniloff and Prof David Tumusiime for their participation and contributions to this study. This project was funded by Business Finland.

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